

Top 4 mobility solutions that will accelerate your logistic business

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Date: MAR 23, 2017

Researchers say that travel and logistics industry play an integral role in the economic growth of the nation. The regular business transaction involves people and goods through air, sea, and surface at a huge scale. Travel and Logistics which is always on the toe and moving requires a streamlined workforce, real-time supply chain visibility and customer satisfaction and utmost transparency.

With the ever-changing industry, the demands of customer are also leading to expectation. In order to respond that, the travel and logistics service providers should invest their time in developing an [enterprise mobility](#) strategy, helping them to stand out in competition. Mobility is acting as a source of nourishment in logistics and transportation industry with an apparent rise in processes and workflows.

Some of the most common challenges faced by travel and logistics service providers:

- High demand for real-time operational visibility and transparency
- Lack of coordination due to complexity in processes and workflow
- Time consumption due to manual processes affecting customer services
- On time goods delivery failure due to excessive processes
- Lack of performance measurement due to absence of techniques like big data and analytics
- Low efficiency and productivity

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How mobility can help travel and logistics service providers to overcome these challenges:

1. Asset real tracking solutions

Keep a track of your shipments and stay update about its exact location through an asset tracking mobile app. This app is built on technology of geo-positioning and identification for tracking the location of your assets. By knowing the exact status of shipment enables to keep deliveries on-time schedule, organize the work process, reduce costs and optimize resource utilization.

2. Warehouse management solutions

This business starts with warehouse and its successful management. It is very important to be aware about the happenings in warehouse at every single minute. Therefore, mobile app helps here to connect with all your assets and notify you real-time conditions. You can keep an eye on your warehouse from a single screen and avoid any glitches that happens being away. Also, it helps in detecting the information of packages and ship them efficiently promising the optimized resource utilization.

3. On-time doorstep delivery

The first step to customer satisfaction is speed in doorstep pick-up and delivery process. A door step delivery mobile app for your business will accelerate your pickup and delivery services. One can scan the product, generate a label, enter delivery details and create an invoice through this mobile app at the customer's doorstep itself. So, the time and efforts can be saved with the direct shipment to the export facility which results in reduced delivery time and superior customer service.

4. Fleet management solutions

An mobile app for fleet management can give you the details of all your drivers, vehicles, and assets inside the vehicles. It facilitates route planning, log times of drivers and deviations leading to manage delivery schedules of all the vehicles. You can track driver performance improving the efficiency of driver and its vehicle. Apart from this it includes well organized fleet management and fuel impacting fleet costs management.

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